

TWINNED By Stars

TWINNEDbySTARS

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900

D2.1 TRAINING PROGRAMME METHODOLOGY

WP2 UPSKILLING AND CAPACITY BUILDING

**UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND BUSINESSES IN ORS**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	08/04/2025	Draft version sent to Steering Committee for comments	Teresa Gubern, Yen Lam González & Matías M. González
1.0	29/04/2025	Final version to be submitted after inclusion of comments from the Steering Committee	Teresa Gubern, Yen Lam González & Matías M. González / Steering Committee members
2.0	09/06/2025	Correction for the training “SEA STARLIGHT” instructor course. Name changed to “Marine StarGuide” instructor course.	Teresa Gubern, Yen Lam González & Matías M. González / Steering Committee members

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	TWINNEDbySTARS
Project Title	Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs
Type of action	EMFAF Project Grants
Topic	EMFAF-2023-PIA-FLAGSHIP-5-OR
Project Start Date	01/10/2023
Project Duration	36 months
Work Package	WP2 UPSKILLING AND CAPACITY BUILDING
Deliverable	D2.1 TRAINING PROGRAMME METHODOLOGY
Due Date	30/04/2025
Submission Date	02/07/2025
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	ULPGC - TIDES (UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA - INSTITUTO DE TURISMO Y DESARROLLO ECONÓMICO SOSTENIBLE)
Version	2.0
Status	Final version
Author(s)	Teresa Gubern; Yen E Lam; Matías M. ULPGC-TIDES Gonzalez
Reviewer(s)	Steering Committee members

¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive

TABLE OF CONTENTS

VERSION HISTORY.....	1
DELIVERABLE INFORMATION.....	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. CONTEXT.....	5
1.1 The Project.....	5
1.2 WP2 scope.....	6
2. METHODOLOGICAL BACKGROUND	6
2.1 Design thinking. Conceptualisation	6
2.2 Empirical applications in tourism product design.....	9
2.3 Design thinking as a course design methodology	10
3. TWINNED BY STARS APPROACH.....	11
3.1 Step 3: Empathise & Ideation – Local workshops.....	14
3.2 Step 4: Prototyping	18
3.3 Logistics.....	21
CONCLUSIONS.....	22
ANNEX.....	23
Email survey 1	23
Email survey 2	24
Pill courses	26
List of enterprises per course.....	29
Courses factsheets.....	34
REFERENCES.....	43

ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CO	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
SC	Steering Committee
OR	Outermost Region
WP	Work Package
AI	Artificial Intelligence

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable D2.1, titled “*Training Programme Methodology*,” is part of Work Package (WP) 2: Upskilling and Capacity Building, task 2.1 ‘Co-design of the training programme’ within the TWINNEDbySTARS project. TWINNEDbySTARS aims to enhance the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector in Europe’s Outermost Regions (ORs) while safeguarding marine biodiversity, preserving cultural heritage, and developing innovative marine-based tourism experiences—including astro-tourism built around ancient navigational routes.

Under WP2, the primary goal is to equip small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), together with other relevant stakeholders, with the skills, and motivation needed to accelerate their digital and ecological transition. In doing so, the project seeks to promote collaborative innovation across ORs, contributing to the sustainable growth of local economies and fostering responsible stewardship of marine environments.

D2.1 specifically outlines the methodology developed to design and deliver the capacity-building program under WP2. It details the **Design Thinking** approach used to tailor training modules to the real-world needs of SMEs, ensuring that each step—empathy, definition, ideation, prototyping, and testing—reflects input gathered through surveys, co-creation workshops, and feedback from the process. The document also highlights key logistical considerations (such as materials, team composition, and accessible workspaces) that underpin successful capacity-building initiatives.

By detailing how the training sessions were conceptualized and implemented, D2.1 provides a blueprint that other regions or sectors may adapt to enhance skills, stimulate innovation, and foster an inclusive transformation process. Future deliverables (D2.2 Report on the conclusions of the training) will build upon this foundation by reporting on the outcomes of the training, participant feedback, and continuous refinements to the methodology, further contributing to the overarching ambitions of TWINNEDbySTARS.

1. CONTEXT

1.1 THE PROJECT

The aim of TWINNEDbySTARS is converting European ORs into an internationally recognized maritime ecotourism destination, which exploits benefits of tourism for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation.

The project builds on the success of previous projects in the Macaronesian region, which have built networks and methodological frameworks to codesign and tune up transformational marine eco-tourism products and activities, involving SMEs located on different islands. Onboard marine environmental education, navigation, respectful sighting, and start light attributes are examples of good practices that combined with interpretative experiences of marine sighting have generated highly satisfactory

tourist experiences and higher environmentally responsible behaviour of SMEs and tourists. TWINNEDbySTARS aims to scale out these experiences at the level of the EU ORs, while fostering the uptake of green and digital innovation by these communities, strengthening partnerships already in operation, capacity building, and opportunities for co-creation.

1.2 WP2 SCOPE

The idea behind WP2 'Upskilling and capacity building' is to implement **a capacity building programme** with tourism firms and other relevant stakeholders to increase awareness, motivation, and skills, providing them with the necessary tools to accelerate digital and ecological transition. The main contribution here is that training courses in this project are not pre-defined, they are designed together with the community of nautical tourism firms in Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands and Martinica.

Additionally, it aims to support them in identifying opportunities for open and collaborative innovation with actors from other ORs, fostering transnational cooperation. Through this process, tourism firms and decision makers will gain the knowledge and resources needed to evaluate and implement concrete actions that enhance circularity, improve efficiency and competitiveness, and contribute to the protection of marine biodiversity at local, regional, and international levels.

2. METHODOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 DESIGN THINKING. CONCEPTUALISATION

Design Thinking is a method for generating innovative ideas focused on understanding and offering solutions to the real needs of users. This action-oriented methodology seeks to create solutions based on identified problems within a specific framework (Brown, 2008). While its more well-known history is relatively recent, its origins can be traced back to before 1960, with early connections to industrial design. During the 1960s in the United States, there were attempts to establish a science around design and link it deeply to people's needs. Figures like Richard Buckminster Fuller and cooperative design groups in Scandinavia were pioneers in these initiatives (Gano, 2015).

Between the 1960s and 1980s, concepts such as innovation, creativity, and multidisciplinary gained traction in the design field, emphasizing that design must adapt to people's needs and their environment. In the 1990s, IDEO popularized Design Thinking as a methodology for innovation, collaborating with companies like Apple (Thomke and Feinberg, 2009). In 2005, Stanford University incorporated Design Thinking into its curriculum, and in 2009, Tim Brown published "Change by Design," which solidified the definition of the method (Auernhammer and Roth 2021).

Today, Design Thinking is employed by companies such as Apple, Google, IBM, Nike, and Zara, standing out as a driver of innovation applicable to diverse fields, from product or service development to process improvement or business model definition (Vinsel, 2018).

The Design Thinking process unfolds through five iterative stages that address complex challenges and problems that are difficult to define and solve (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Design thinking methodology. Source: Vinsel, 2018.

As you can see on Figure 1, each stage either goes up (divergent) or down (convergent) from getting lot of information from users (divergent) to filtering and defining the more important ones (convergent) to brainstorming all sort of ideas to tackle the issue or need seen on the two steps before where all ideas are welcome (divergent) to then again only choosing the most realistic ones (convergent) to convert into prototypes and test them.

In the process of Design thinking, the success also depends on other logistic factors that are key and must be prepared in advance:

- **Materials:** Accessible tools, sufficient to be able to work properly without unnecessary pauses to fetch materials.
- **Teamwork:** Diversity of perspectives and at least one member knowledgeable in the methodology.
- **Space:** A large, bright, and inspiring environment.
- **Attitude:** Empathy, curiosity, observation, optimism, and a willingness to experiment and learn from mistakes.

The process is also supported by different tools and techniques (as shown in Figure 1). A non-exhaustive list of other techniques that can be utilised in each phase are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Tools and techniques for design thinking.

Empathy	Definition	Ideation	Prototyping	Testing
Actor mapping	Cognitive Immersion	Constructive interaction	Mind mapping	Moodboards
Covert observation	What, how, why?	Qualitative interview script	Qualitative interviews	Extreme users
Storytelling	Customer journey	Lotus flower	World café	Map of the present, map of the future
focus groups	Technique of the 5 Why?	Toolkit	Ishikawa or cause and effect diagram	Parallel analysis
“Weighted weighting methods”	Technique of the 5 What for?	Would be / Would not be	Porter's Diagram	Swot Matrix
Business model canvas	Customer attraction map	inside / outside	Priority diagram	Value curves
Glocal	AEIOU	Dimensional analysis	Safari	Blueprint
Selection by classification	Context maps	Drawing of the problem	Spectrum map	My turn
Phillips 6/6	Red and green cards	Media research	Statistics	Trend study
Research on referents	Competition analysis	Expert interviews	Trend matrix	Benchmark
Notes P.O.E.M.S.	Interviews with photos	Evocative images	Start, stop, continue	Shadowing
Systems thinking	Delphi method	Pestel o Pestal Analysis		

2.2 EMPIRICAL APPLICATIONS IN TOURISM PRODUCT DESIGN

Design Thinking can be applied to any field or sector. Initially focused on improving industrial design, its application has expanded to diverse areas such as consumer products, digital services, education, health, entertainment, banking, transportation, and more (Micheli et al, 2019). In tourism, Design Thinking is used for offering innovative approaches to service design, user experience optimization, and the creation of new business models. Examples include platforms like Airbnb, which have revolutionized the hospitality sector by using this methodology to adapt their services to the evolving needs of users (Lalicic et al, 2021).

In tourism, Design Thinking helps address challenges ranging from logistics and visitor flow to customer satisfaction, environmental sustainability, and even community engagement.

A key feature of Design Thinking in tourism is its focus on empathizing with users' (i.e., tourists' and local stakeholders') real needs and motivations, prototyping solutions that seamlessly fit into their travel or leisure experiences, and then continuously testing and refining those solutions. This approach also promotes collaboration among stakeholders—both public and private—allowing for ideas that combine multiple perspectives (Enzyme Advising Group, 2023; Watch&Act, n.d).

From these projects, the following insight was driven:

- Community and stakeholder engagement is key. For empathy we might not only need the insight of the tourists themselves but also from other actors, as this broadens the perspectives included in the design, creating solutions locally relevant and sustainable (López and Pereyra, 2019).

A prominent example is the study conducted in the city of Valencia, where a multidisciplinary team used this methodology to address **safety issues in bicycle tourism**. Through empathy and ideation, a mobile application was designed that provided real-time information on safe routes, thus improving both the experience and the safety of the tourist (López and Pereyra, 2019). Another revealing case is the **'Wenuleufu' project** in Chile, which applied service design thinking to redesign the rafting experience on the Bueno River. In this case, the emotional dimension of the client was prioritised, achieving a more immersive and satisfactory tourism proposal (Covarrubias, 2020). Likewise, in Peru, a study carried out with tourism students showed how the joint use of Lean Startup and Design Thinking fostered **entrepreneurship**, by allowing the development of viable tourism business ideas without requiring large initial investments, and easily adapting to changes in the environment (Pacompa & Ponce, 2019). These examples illustrate how the methodology not only improves existing services, but also drives new ways of thinking about tourism through innovation and sustainability.

2.3 DESIGN THINKING AS A COURSE DESIGN METHODOLOGY

In education, Design Thinking facilitates the creation of programs tailored to students, fosters critical thinking, and improves teaching methodologies. Interactive tools and digital platforms have been designed to make learning more accessible and meaningful. This approach allows not only to rethink content, but also how it is taught, promoting participation, creativity and critical thinking. (Zupan & Nabergoj, 2022).

This methodology encourages teamwork, empathy and the ability to experiment without fear of making mistakes (Panke 2019). Moreover, Design Thinking helps training processes to be more dynamic and practical, and is very much in line with the current challenges of education, such as the need to promote transversal skills, to work collaboratively or to face complex problems with creative solutions (Panke 2019).

Some examples of how Design THinkin has been used in educational settings are as follows:

The **Community Drive project** in Denmark, where students addressed real urban challenges through collaborative and participatory design processes. This experience not only fostered creative confidence, but also reinforced key 21st-century skills such as collaboration, critical thinking, and civic engagement (Rusmann & Ejsing-Duun, 2022).

The **Game-Based Learning project**, where students engaged with digital environments like *Minecraft* to design games or build inside them. These playful, inquiry-based activities allowed learners to explore design cycles in a motivating and interactive way (Rusmann & Ejsing-Duun, 2022).

In a middle school context, **Goldman et al. (2009)** implemented Design Thinking in the classroom and found that students developed a deeper understanding of how to approach complex problems by reflecting not just on what to solve, but on how to frame and think through the problem itself.

3. TWINNED BY STARS APPROACH

In order to effectively implement the Design Thinking methodology in the framework of WP2, the traditional five-step process was adapted to the specific needs of the ORs and the nautical tourism sector. This adaptation was essential to adequately involve local stakeholders, generate community, and ensure the relevance of the trainings. The approach adopted was structured in four iterative phases:

Figure 2. Twinned By Stars Approach.

Step 1: Exploration

Before starting any empathy phase, a preliminary exploration phase was developed to raise awareness and create a community interested in TWINNEDbySTARS. This phase included:

- Direct communication with key companies and institutions in the sector.
- Explanation of the purpose of the project and concrete benefits of participating.
- Dissemination of the training and co-creation procedure (certification for employees, individual evaluations, and so on).

Figure 3. Step 1: exploration.

The way the companies and all kind of stakeholders joined the project and started becoming part of our community was by filling a **first survey** where we collected their data, situation, best practices and needs and would have their contact details for future communication.

This stage was crucial for the actors to understand the context of the project, generating confidence and predisposition to actively participate in the following phases. All this was helped through with WP5 communication and WP1 Stakeholder engagement activities.

The emails sent for survey 1 and the survey can be checked on the [Annex](#).

Step 2: Engagement-incentives

Once the community was created, incentive actions were designed to strengthen companies' engagement in the project and also motivate them to provide more information about their needs and desires. This included:

Figure 4. Step 2: engagement-incentives

Survey 2, which aimed at collecting specific interests, best practices and challenges in the sector of the companies itself. On survey 1 we gathered information from all types of stakeholders whereas on survey 2 we just focused on the companies itself.

As a reward from filling in survey 2, companies received exclusive access to "pill courses"—concise training capsules offering one-hour introductory sessions on topics such as the circular economy, digital innovation, and maritime tourism best practices, which were examples of future courses (if they were interested). The intention to attend these courses was also a measure of their potential interest in the topics (astro-sailing, or digital campaigns).

As well as with Step 1, this step was supported by WP1 stakeholder engagement activities, WP5 communication and WP4 coordination. Examples of emails to survey 2 are attached in the [Annex](#).

Delivered in Spanish with simultaneous translation into Portuguese and French, and with recordings available for later review, these masterclasses were designed to spark interest and help businesses identify areas for further development. Titles of the two alternative courses were: 'Astrotourism and its potential for your business' (Figure 5) & 'Online tactics to attract customers' (Figure 6).

In this process, there was equal interest in both courses, reaching to 66 companies who registered in one or two courses and receive the masterclass (live or recorded). To the live part we had 13 SMEs in the autonomous one and 41 on the digital campaign one.

Figure 5. Masterclass on Astrotourism

Figure 6. Masterclass on Digital Campaigns.

3.1 STEP 3: EMPATHISE & IDEATION – LOCAL WORKSHOPS

Figure 7. Step 3. Empathize & Ideate

This central phase of the TWINNEDbySTARS approach was developed through four co-creation workshops organised in the framework of WP3 - Generation of new spaces for co-creation of new products and new nautical tourism, task 3.2, in which a specific space was dedicated to identifying and discussing the training needs of the

nautical companies in each one of our ORs. This was done during the second day of the workshops or, in the case of Azores, coinciding with a General Meeting of partners, the workshop was carried in one day, and training discussion during the second part of the day as you can see on Figure 8:

Figure 8. Co-creation workshops design.

The dates of the four workshops are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Co-creation workshops dates.

This organization was useful, as previous discussions about new tourism products were a trigger for the empathy phase and prepared the ground for a more active and contextualized participation.

The discussions and debate about the training needs, were accompanied by a self-assessment tool. This was the third survey (survey 3) that the enterprises filled in since the beginning of the process. This was designed to self-assess the positioning of each company in terms of sustainability and circularity. This tool was filled in directly by the attending companies, while the other key actors (non-business stakeholders) completed it in relation to their general perception of these issues. This provided us with both an internal and external view of the nautical tourism ecosystem in each region.

Self assessment tool for nautical tourism companies

From Take Make Dispose to ♠REUSE ♠ RETHINK ♠REVALUE ♠REGENERATE

Figure 10. Self-assessment tool – sections of the questionnaire.

The self-assessment tool was adapted from the [INCIRCLE's Circular Tourism Tools](#), built within a European project (Med Interreg), and dedicated to hotels or tourism destinations. In our project we adapted it to the nautical tourism context.

In the TWINNEDbySTARS version, the four capitals were maintained but also a key fifth element was introduced: Digital Maturity, reflecting the growing importance of digital transformation for small tourism enterprises. Another key difference is two sides approach:

- Enterprises evaluate their own practices in sustainability and digital readiness.
- Stakeholders assess how their region is performing overall, offering an external perspective.

Table 2. Self-assessment surveys' links.

	ENTERPRISES	OTHER STAKEHOLDERS
CANARY ISLANDS	https://forms.gle/UH5AbFBm53oDGgGX9	https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSff9QPcY5Tyg0Q5qwArdHzd7gAggimNVOP1RNmTH6thpwkUWw/viewform?pli=1
MADEIRA & AZORES	https://forms.gle/Uooxygx9XgUxvFZW7	https://forms.gle/Do52XsYULQPn6ogDA
MARTINICA	https://forms.gle/digQJ3UPcErnr9v19	https://forms.gle/B26hGMPnKkMse9fQ8

In each workshop, the discussion revolved around the responses of these surveys, alongside with all the previous information gathered in previous steps (Survey 1 and 2). This generated a dynamic debate on the current needs of the companies and helped to collectively identify the most relevant training priorities.

These resulted in the following general need that are common for all regions:

1. **Artificial Intelligence (AI).** Course on AI tools for business management Automation of processes such as customer requests and bookings, social media and email campaigns, regular communications with customers.
2. **Energy efficiency planning:** Lack of efficiency plans for vessels, particularly motor vessels. Need for training in alternative or energy-saving methods.
3. **Technical assistance for electric motors under varying weather conditions:** Difficulty in maintaining electric motors due to lack of local infrastructure, knowledge and human resources. Dependence on the mainland for repairs and upgrades.
4. **Digital marketing and strategy:** Need for a well-defined marketing strategy using social media and AI. Suggested use of platforms such as Fiverr, Cyber, Upwork, Asana and Malt for wider distribution and management.
5. **Certification across regions:** Interest in certifications that cover all regions or a certification standard (such as TbS) that includes companies within their network.

These needs lead to the definition of potential trainings:

Figure 11. Potential trainings defined at the co-creation workshops.

3.2 STEP 4: PROTOTYPING

Following its prototype nature, all of the above-mentioned courses were designed and offered but only took place if there was some interest. To avoid organizing courses without an audience. However, there was indeed great interest to all of them.

Below there are the courses designed up until April 2025, more insights can be retrieved from the future deliverable 'D2.2 Report on the conclusions of the training'. All sessions were recorded for those unable to attend and included translations into Portuguese and French.

IA FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

The objective of these courses was to enable nautical SMEs to use artificial intelligence (AI) and automation tools to improve their social media presence (Facebook, Instagram, etc.) and digital campaigns (Ads, SEM, SEO). Following the co-creation workshops, it became clear that smaller companies with limited crews urgently needed support to keep up with their digital marketing.

FREE COURSE

USE OF AI IN DIGITAL COMMUNICATION

<p>TRAINER Juan Ma Peralta</p> <p>FORMAT Online</p> <p>DURATION 2 sessions 1h 30 min each</p>	<p>TOOLS Google Analytics, Facebook Insights, Social media management platforms: Hootsuite, Buffer, Sprout Social...</p>
<p>WHAT WILL WE SEE IN THE SESSIONS?</p> <p>It will address both the practical use of these tools and strategies for integrating them into the digital campaigns of companies in the tourism sector.</p>	<p>WHAT WILL WE SEE IN THE SESSIONS?</p> <p>It will explain, for example, how to use Google Analytics to interpret key metrics, or how Hootsuite can facilitate content management and scheduling, and a comparison of costs and benefits between free and premium versions will be made.</p>
<p>SAVE TIME AND RESOURCES. OPTIMISE YOUR DIGITAL CAMPAIGNS</p> <p>Increase the efficiency of your campaigns, save time with automation, improve your online visibility and gain an edge in the industry. Join us!</p>	<p>REGISTER YOUR TEAM!</p> <p>Register as many people as you want and we will inform you soon about the details of when and how.</p>

Training accredited by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
Registered participants will have access to a recording of the course in case they are unable to attend.

FREE COURSE

YOUR DIGITAL COMPASS: AI TO AUTOMATE SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

<p>TRAINER Enuno de Raquel Vázquez</p> <p>FORMAT Online</p> <p>DURATION 2 sessions 1h 30 min each</p>	<p>TOOLS • Canva • Metricool • ChatGPT</p>
<p>SESSION 1. INTRODUCTION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and key concepts • Definition of a digital strategy (with AI) • Case studies and personalisation 	<p>SESSION 2. OPTIMISATION AND AUTOMATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample examples created by participants • Planning and automation of content • Closing (review, tips and questions)
<p>OVERCOMING FEAR OF TECHNOLOGY</p> <p>Help yourself with this course to automate your social media campaign.</p>	<p>REGISTER YOUR TEAM!</p> <p>Register as many people as you want and we will inform you soon about the details of when and how.</p>

Training accredited by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
Registered participants will have access to a recording of the course in case they are unable to attend.

Figure 12. Factsheets to promote the AI courses.

Four sessions, two per topic, were given, 1,5 hours each. In total: 6 hours. Their course sheet and other information can be found in the [Annex](#).

We shared the registration link via:

1. An email campaign to the companies that participated in our co-creation workshops
2. A general email blast to our entire database
3. A poster published on the FPCT website, distributed by CMC, and shared by project partners
4. Social media channels and website

Registration opened on February 20, 2025, and closed on March 15, 2025. In total, we received **154 registrations from 68 different enterprises**.

HYDROPHONES

The objective of this session was to Incorporate hydrophones into whale watching activities, adding an educational and sensory element to deepen tourists’ connection with the marine environment. As this topic was of great interest in the co-creation workshops but the companies didn’t manage to find a way to make it part of the product, it was then decided to transform it into this session.

Course sheet in the [Annex](#).

Date: May 2025

MARINE STARGUIDE

The objective was to provide specialized knowledge in maritime astro-tourism, combining nighttime navigation with stargazing and environmental awareness.

This certification program is delivered in collaboration with experts in nautical astronomy and astro-tourism. In addition to theoretical content, participants engage in one practical activity (guided night-time sailing) to consolidate newly acquired skills.

Course sheet in the [Annex](#).

Date: 22,23,24, 28, 29, 30 April 2025 + practical outing in each region.

Canary Islands: May 2025

Azores: May-June 2025

Madeira May-June 2025

Martinique: October 2025 (along with the consortium meeting)

Table 3. MARINE STARGUIDE certification courses.

SUBJECT	DURATION	PROFESSOR
History of navigation	2 hours	Xavier Martínez
Astronomical tourism and the role of Certifications	1 hour	Xavier Martínez
Nautical astro-tourism marketing and public speaking communication skills	3 hours	Gerard Martínez
Mythology in astronomical navigation	1.5 hours	Naty Sánchez
History of astronomy	2 hours	Javier Ares

Measuring space-time	1.5 hours	Javier Ares
How to find our way in the sky	1.5 hours	Javier Ares
Preparing an observation with Stellarium	1.5 hours	Javier Ares
Basic Astronomy Course	1.5 hours	Javier Ares
Light pollution	1 hours	Javier Romero
The Solar System	1.5 hours	Javier Ares

3.3 LOGISTICS

Regarding the logistical aspects of our process:

- **Materials:** for that matter interactive tools like genially were used, as well as the usual paper and notes, to make it more accessible and visually easy to comprehend.
- **Team:** Diversity of perspectives and at least one member knowledgeable in the methodology. For that reason, we managed to include at least one partner from the private sector and one from the public sector not only in the workshops as a whole but in each working table.
- **Space:** A large, bright, and inspiring environment. For that we managed to have adequate spaces in each region, with plenty of room to work in each workshop.
- **Attitude:** Participants were encouraged to embrace an open mindset, where there were no "right" or "wrong" answers. The focus was on collaborative thinking and imagination, ensuring that enterprises could freely express their needs. This approach helped capture valuable insights throughout the design thinking process.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of Design Thinking within the TWINNEDbySTARS project has successfully enabled the definition of training content that is both practical and context-specific. More importantly, it fostered the creation of a learning community rooted in co-creation, empowering SMEs to actively shape their own capacity-building journey rather than passively receiving external training offers.

The participatory approach adopted ensured that the training courses were directly aligned with the expressed needs, challenges, and aspirations of nautical tourism enterprises across the Outermost Regions. The multi-stage methodology—consisting of exploration, engagement, empathy, ideation, and prototyping—allowed us to deeply understand the current state of digital maturity, circularity, and innovation readiness among participants.

Key takeaways from this process include:

- Early and continuous engagement of SMEs significantly improves participation and ownership.
- Linking short-term incentives (e.g., "pill courses") to longer-term co-creation goals is a powerful catalyst for sustained involvement.
- Combining internal (self-assessment by companies) and external (stakeholder feedback) evaluations offers a richer, more actionable diagnosis of ecosystem needs.
- A flexible, needs-driven training catalogue outperforms a predefined set of courses in dynamic contexts like tourism innovation.

The logistics and facilitation strategies employed (diverse teams, open environments, flexible materials, translation) also proved critical to maintaining a creative and productive working atmosphere during workshops and trainings.

The learnings and insights gathered through this methodology will directly feed into Deliverable D2.2, where the training results, participant feedback, and the final evaluation of the implemented methodology will be presented in detail.

ANNEX.

EMAIL SURVEY 1

EMAIL to all STAKEHOLDERS

Subject: 🌟 TWINNEDbySTARS invitation to join the project network

Dear [entity's name],

Since [TbS's partner], we are participating in a new EU project, [TWINNEDbySTARS](#), aiming at increasing the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector, through the promotion of digitalisation, circularity and innovation, and the co-creation of new products, services and partnerships in Europe's Outermost Regions.

The [consortium](#) of the project is composed by several entities of the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores, and Martinique. But the participation of experts, academics, industry and society representatives and policymakers is crucial to ensure a real process of social innovation.

Considering your path in the nautical and marine tourism activities we would like to invite you to join the TWINNEDbySTARS network and profit of information, outputs, news and much more. I strongly believe that your enrolment will help us to maximize the impact of the project.

I invite you also to **subscribe to this [form](#) to become part of our project network**, receive newsletters, and being re-contacted to take part in our future activities and events.

For more information about the benefits of your participation in the TWINNEDbySTARS project, please have a look at the leaflet attached.

Many thanks in advance and look forward to engaging with you in our next project activities.

Name

EMAIL SURVEY 2

Email to only the enterprises

Exclusive TWINNEDbySTARS for you

Dear [name],

We couldn't be happier to have you on board. Thank you for your subscription and interest in TWINNEDbySTARS.

You are receiving this email because we have identified that you are a company operating in the marine-maritime environment and are based in the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores or Martinique.

If so, you are a key player in our project and it is with great enthusiasm that we write to you to invite you to become part of our SME network as well.

We strongly believe that any contribution you make will help us to maximise the impact of the network, and you could also benefit directly from our activities.

What advantages do you get from belonging to the TWINNEDbySTARS SME Network?

- Receive technical support and coaching to apply for certifications or awards.
- Your whole team can participate in free training courses on topics of common interest, certified by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
- Opportunity to receive or mentor other companies on solutions and technologies that respond to common needs.
- Participate in exchange events, fairs and open innovation workshops at international level with other companies in the sector.
- Receive technical support and accompaniment to launch business ideas to the market together with other companies (Canary Islands-Azores-Madeira and Martinique multideestination experiences).

Participation is free of charge, no co-financing is required.

What do you have to do?

For the moment fill in this form: [EUSurvey - Survey \(europa.eu\)](#). With this you would be applying for membership in the SME Network of the project.

If you complete the questionnaire, you will automatically win a place in a first pillar course for you and your team, which will surely contribute to a career plan within the company. The courses are coordinated by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.

Fill in the survey and select your preferred course [HERE](#)

We look forward to working together.

Best regards,

TWINNEDbySTARS team

For any questions contact us at twinnedbystars@gmail.com

 ¡EXCLUSIVE! Benefits for your team

Dear **Name**,

We couldn't be happier to have you on board. Thanks for your subscription and interest in TWINNEDbySTARS

You receive this email because we have identified that you are a nautical SME (Small Medium Enterprise operating in the marine-maritime environment) and are based in the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores or Martinica.

If this is so, you are a key player in our project and we are reaching out to you with great enthusiasm to invite you to be also a part of our hub of SMEs.

Why Your Involvement Matters:

TWINNEDbySTARS aims at boosting the uptake of digitalisation, circularity and innovation in SMEs operating in marine and coastal environments in the Atlantic region. During the upcoming months we will deploy a first evaluation stage and organise matchmaking events to create together with you the best action plan for the hub.

Benefits of Joining the TWINNEDbySTARS' hub of SMEs **(see leaflet attached)**

Your participation is free of charge, no co-financing is required, only the motivation to innovate and grow.

Next Steps: If you are interested in joining us on this exciting journey, please fill-in this [form](#)

By completing the questionnaire, you automatically win a place in an online masterclass session certified by the school Nautic Ocean (Barcelona) and the University of las Palmas de Gran Canaria from Spain. This session is open to your team and free of charge.

Fill-in the survey and select your preferred course.

We look forward to the possibility of working together.

Best regards,

TWINNEDbySTARS team

For any questions contact us at twinnedbystars@gmail.com

PILL COURSES

The pill courses were part of the second step “engagement-incentives”. They provided introductory sessions on topics related to the circular economy, digital innovation, and best practices relevant to the maritime tourism sector. These pill courses were given as incentives to companies to fill out survey 2. The sessions were one hour long and given in Spanish with simultaneous translation.

Experimentation and online tactics to attract more customers

- Videos.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=06pznWbuuBI>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ubcq3LQL2Dw>

Astroturism and its potential for your business

- Video.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=02m1pDjclc>

Inscription list

Name of your company	Region
Associação para o Desenvolvimento e Formação do Mar dos Açores	Azores
Azores Boat Adventures	Azores
Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores	Azores
Clube Naval de Vila Franca do Campo	Azores
DIVE AZORES LDA	Azores
Floresfishing	Azores
Galeão Tropical Unipessoal, Lda	Azores
House Boat & Sea	Azores
Marco André Puim Nunes	Azores
Norberto Diver - Actividades Marítimas Lda.	Azores
Paulo Luís Sousa - Actividades Marítimo Turísticas (Seascape Sharing Experiences)	Azores
Pico Outdoor	Azores
Portos dos Açores, S. A.	Azores
Academia arcos	Canarias
ACOSTA INGENIERÍA MARÍTIMA S.L.U. (BLUEMATT)	Canarias

AENAUTICA. FEMEPA	Canarias
Aquatera Atlántico	Canarias
Biocean Whale Watching and Marine Science	Canarias
BLANCOMAR NAUTICA, SL.	Canarias
Canary on board	Canarias
DISTRIMAR	Canarias
Dolphin and whales	Canarias
elittoral	Canarias
Federación Turística de Lanzarote / Federación Profesional Canaria de centros de buceo recreativos / Asociación de Turismo Náutico de Canarias CANARINAUTIC	Canarias
Fifodivingshop	Canarias
Financiate y crece	Canarias
Global port canary islands	Canarias
Hiades Business Patterns SL	Canarias
Innovamarina	Canarias
ISM	Canarias
Keep Sailing	Canarias
Motonautica las palmas	Canarias
Motores y embarcaciones ALONAUTICA	Canarias
NÁUTICA NIVARIA SLU	Canarias
Pleyone Management Capital SL	Canarias
Princesa Ico excursiones	Canarias
PUERTO DEPORTIVO PASITO BLANCO (CANARIAS) S.L.U.	Canarias
Surf-Canaries	Canarias
Tour Man	Canarias
Associação MarinaFunchal	Madeira
Gavião Madeira	Madeira
Green Storm	Madeira
HAPPY HOUR	Madeira
Magic Dolphin	Madeira
Mr.Humb Unipessoal Lda	Madeira
Nautisantos Act Desportivas, Lda	Madeira

NOMAD RESPONSE LDA	Madeira
Porto Santo Sub	Madeira
Sea Lá Vie	Madeira
Ventura Nature Emotions	Madeira
Visões Aquadelicas, actividades marítima turísticas, Lda.	Madeira
VMT Madeira	Madeira
CAP ANTILLES INTERNATIONAL – SARL	Martinique
CAP caravelle	Martinique
Carbet des Sciences	Martinique
CENTRALE DU BATEAU	Martinique
Comité Martiniquais du Tourisme	Martinique
LA PIROGUE KALINA	Martinique
LA SURVY SARL	Martinique
LES TI FUMES DE CLEMENT	Martinique
PUNCH CROISIERES	Martinique
SARL KATA MAMBO	Martinique
SEAFRET CARAIBES	Martinique
Sites ayant une vocation scientifique liée à l'observation du volcan / Maison des Volcans / Centre de découverte des sciences de la terre – CDST / Observatoire du Morne des Cadets	Martinique
SKIPPER ANTILLES CHARTER	Martinique
SNSM DE FORT DE FRANCE – LES SAUVETEURS EN MER	Martinique

Total: 66 entreprises.

LIST OF ENTERPRISES PER COURSE

Use of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism

ENTERPRISE	REGION
ACIF-CCIM	MADEIRA
alisios sailing center	CANARIAS
Ana Pontes & Filhos Unipessoal, Lda.	MADEIRA
APRAM - Portos da Madeira, SA	MADEIRA
Arrecifal Centro de Buceo	CANARIAS
Associação MarinaFunchal	MADEIRA
ASSOCIATION LYMPH	MARTINIQUE
ASTILLEROS CANARIOS SA	CANARIAS
Azorean Seascape	AÇORES
Azores Boat Adventures	AÇORES
Azores Experiences	AÇORES
AZORES SUB Dive Center	AÇORES
AZORES SUB LDA	AÇORES
BIOSEAN Whale Watching & Marine Science	CANARIAS
Blancomar Nautica	CANARIAS
Brava Onda	MADEIRA
C-Adventures	MADEIRA
CANARSHIP	CANARIAS
Cisc consultoría y servicios	CANARIAS
Clube Naval de Santa Maria	AÇORES
Clúster Marítimo de Canarias	CANARIAS
Discover Experience	AÇORES
Dive Around Madeira	MADEIRA
Dolphin and Whales	CANARIAS
Econaturismo Lda, SeaEO-Tours	LISBOA
Espírito Azul, Lda	AÇORES
Floresfishing	AÇORES
Freelancer	MADEIRA
Freelancer	MADEIRA
Freelancer	MADEIRA
Freelancer	CANARIAS
Fun Activities Azores Adventures	AÇORES
Grupo catamaran excursion, s.l.	CANARIAS
Haliotis	AÇORES Y MADEIRA
Hominis natura	AÇORES
INCARGO SL	CANARIAS
João Moreira	AÇORES
Kayak Life	MADEIRA
Keep Sailing	CANARIAS
la Pirogue Kalina	MARTINIQUE

Madeira Boat Rentals	MADEIRA
Madeira Sea Fishing (Neptuno Admirável)	MADEIRA
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	MADEIRA
Madeiratlanticharters lda	MADEIRA
Marciisviagens	MADIERA
Naturalist, Science & Tourism	AÇORES
Nautisantos, Lda	MADEIRA
Nexus corporation business S.A.S	COLOMBIA
Observatório do Mar dos Açores	AÇORES
OceanEye Azores	AÇORES
Oceano de experiencias	CANARIAS
On Tales	MADEIRA
Radarvirtual	MADEIRA
REGIE AUTONOME PORT DE PLAISANCE – MARINA DE LA POINTE DU BOUT	MARTINIQUE
Sea Explorers Azores	AÇORES
SeaEO Tours	LISBOA
Surf Canaries	CANARIAS
Xanaia	AÇORES

Participants enregistered: 77

Enterprises enlisted: 54

Freelancers: 4

Your Digital Compass: AI For Successful Social Media Navigation

ENTERPRISE	REGION
Abrandia S.L	CANARIAS
ACIF-CCIM	MADEIRA
Ana Pontes & Filhos Unipessoal, Lda.	MADEIRA
Argencan	CANARIAS
Arrecifal Centro de Buceo	CANARIAS
ASTILLEROS CANARIOS SA	CANARIAS
Azores Boat Adventures	AÇORES
Azores Experiences	AÇORES
AZORES SUB LDA	AÇORES
Blancomar Nautica	CANARIAS
Brava Onda	MADEIRA
C-Adventures	BRASIL
CANARSHIP	CANARIAS
CCI Martinique	MARTINIQUE
CLÚSTER MARÍTIMO DE CANARIAS	CANARIAS
Dive Around Madeira	MADEIRA
Econauturismo Lda, SeaEO-Tours	LISBOA
Floresfishing	AÇORES

Freelancer	MADEIRA
Freelancer	MADEIRA
Fun Activities Azores Adventures	AÇORES
Haliotis	AÇORES Y MADEIRA
Hominis natura	AÇORES
Instituto Profissional de Transportes e Logística da Madeira	MADEIRA
Jo&Elio por Puerto Deportivo Los Gigantes	CANARIAS
Kayak Azores Adventure	AÇORES
Kayak Life	MADEIRA
Keep Sailing	CANARIAS
la PIROGUE KALINA	MARTINIQUE
Madeira Boat Rentals	MADEIRA
Madeira Sea Fishing (Neptuno Admirável)	MADEIRA
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	MADEIRA
Marciisviagens	MADEIRA
Meridiano cero	CANARIAS
Mr.Humb unipessoal Ida	MADEIRA
Naturalist Lda.	AÇORES
Naturalist, Science & Tourism	AÇORES
Nautic Ocean	CANARIAS
Nautisantos, Lda	MADEIRA
Observatório do Mar dos Açores	AÇORES
OceanEye Azores	AÇORES
Oceano de experiencias	BALEARES
On Tales	MADEIRA
Radarvirtual	MADEIRA
REGIE AUTONOME PORT DE PLAISANCE - MARINA DE LA POINTE DU BOUT	MARTINIQUE
Sea Riders Dive Center	AÇORES
Steffi Denecker, Unipessoal, Lda - Hominis natura	AÇORES
Surf Canaries	CANARIAS
Universidad de Lima	LIMA
Volna voyage	AÇORES
Xanaia	AÇORES

Participants enregistered: 77

Enterprises enlisted: 49

Freelancers: 2

MARINE STARGUIDE

The online part of this course will be open until the end of December 2025. In June the practical part will take place in Madeira and Azores. In Martinica it will take place in October, along with the consortium meeting. In Canarias it will take place before the end of the year.

There will be one practical part per region. After the practical part is done, the online part will be open to viewers on our website

At the moment, these were the enterprises enlisted:

Enterprise	Region
Albatros y Gaviotas	Canarias
Biosean Whale Watching and Marine Science	Canarias
CLÚSTER MARÍTIMO DE CANARIAS	Canarias
COLLECTIVITE TERRITORIALE DE MARTINIQUE	Martinique
Dolphin and Whales	Canarias
GuiaNatura EcoTourism	Canarias
Hominis natura	Açores
Horizonte Celeste	Madeira
Keep Sailing	Canarias
LA PIROGUE KALINA	Martinique
Longitude 31	Açores
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	Madeira
MBR	Madeira
Medusa & Químera Lda	Madeira
Oceanodroma, Lda	Madeira
Prácticos de El Hierro SLPU (Serea)	Canarias
Sailingside	Açores
SKIPPER ANTILLES CHARTER	Martinique
Sunkiss Sailing	Madeira
ULPGC	Canarias

Participants enregistered: 34

Enterprises enlisted: 20

COURSES FACTSHEETS

COURSE: USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIGITAL COMMUNICATION FOR NAUTICAL TOURISM

Course: Use of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism		Trainer/s: Juan Ma Peral & Gerard Martínez
Format: Online	Language: Spanish	Translation: into French and Portuguese.
<p>User Profile:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small companies in the nautical tourism sector in the Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira and Martinique. • Low level of prior knowledge. 		
<p>Content:</p> <p>Introduction to AI in Digital Marketing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic concepts and relevance in the digital environment. <p>Tools and Campaign Automation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of tools for ADS, SEM, SEO and web positioning. <p>Optimisation and Personalisation Strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How AI can improve the segmentation and personalisation of campaigns. <p>Case Study:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time analysis of a case study (e.g. a diving company in the Canary Islands) and discussion of results. 		
Duration: 2 sessions of 1h 30 min. each.	<p>Activities to Perform and Duration of Each:</p> <p>Theoretical Session (1h30):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual presentation with key concepts and examples of tools. <p>Practical Session (1h30):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive seminar and live demonstration of a practical case study. 	
Requirements:	<p>Internet connection and computer.</p> <p>Basic knowledge of digital communication (no advanced experience required).</p>	

	Interest in improving digital presence through the use of IA tools.
General objective:	Empower small nautical businesses to use artificial intelligence in their social media campaigns, improving their visibility and efficiency.
Expected outcomes of the course:	<p>Understand the fundamental principles of artificial intelligence applied to digital marketing.</p> <p>Identify and use advanced automation and analysis tools to optimise social media campaigns.</p> <p>Develop personalised and effective strategies to improve online positioning.</p> <p>Immediately apply the knowledge acquired through a real case study.</p>
Types of tools to use and cost for companies	<p>Data analysis tools: Google Analytics, Facebook Insights.</p> <p>Social media management platforms: Hootsuite, Buffer. Campaign optimisation solutions with AI.</p> <p>Cost: Free and trial versions are available, but premium versions tend to offer better results (variable cost).</p>
Alternative and Complementary Tools	<p>Data Analytics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adobe Analytics and Mixpanel: Offer deeper and more personalised analytics to understand user behaviour. <p>Social Media Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sprout Social and Later: These platforms integrate advanced monitoring and analytics features, with a focus on interaction and audience management. <p>Campaign Optimisation with AI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HubSpot Marketing Hub, SEMrush or Albert: Tools that use artificial intelligence to optimise targeting, improve SEO and automate campaigns, providing measurable results.
What will attendees see?	In the sessions, I will address both the practical use of these tools and strategies for integrating them into the digital campaigns of companies in the tourism sector. We will explain, for example, how to use Google Analytics to interpret key metrics, or how Hootsuite can facilitate the management and programming of content, and a comparison of costs and benefits between the free and premium versions will be made.
Benefit to the	<p>Greater efficiency and effectiveness in your digital campaigns.</p> <p>Saving time and resources by automating tasks.</p>

enterprises	Increased visibility and better online positioning. Gaining a competitive advantage in the nautical tourism sector.
Link to video	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/23258tqb62idm99jpg9d1/AAbFG920kDsaLJdH4X6M7Gs?rlkey=ln6o8gwzy3g4qwgqyer37l5cuf&dl=0
Link to materials	ChatGPT . https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/34doafug2pxrjoj3kfvav/AIKSmSmmko55Nx3g4isqvHw?rlkey=k8ozrovedbh5jzcnls7yrqqnc&dl=0 Google Ads. https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/r9rkdjq02m20nnp93mgdv/AN-1BWO7KAc_BVd7GXVTJJQ?rlkey=8a46tkltw9hgymjymlsdvqotl&dl=0

COURSE FACT SHEET – YOUR DIGITAL COMPASS: AI FOR SUCCESSFUL SOCIAL MEDIA NAVIGATION

Course Your Digital Compass: AI for successful social media navigation		Trainer: Enuno by Raquel Vázquez
Format: Online	Language: Spanish	Translation to Portuguese & French.
User Profile: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small companies in the nautical tourism sector in the Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira and Martinique. - Low level of prior knowledge. 		
Content: Introduction and basic application of AI (ChatGPT): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overcoming the fear of technology. - Defining a digital strategy using AI. - Creation of effective publications and promotional texts. Content plan with AI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating monthly content plans. - Use of visual tools and scheduling of publications. • Batch content generation. 		

<p>Duration: 2 sessions of 1h 30 min each.</p>	<p>Session 1: Introduction and basic application of AI (90 minutes)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction and key concepts (10 minutes): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Presentation of the course and its relevance for small businesses. 2. Definition of a digital strategy using AI (50 minutes): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Identification of the ideal audience and their needs. o Practical exercise to define the tone and style of communication adapted to each company. o Use of ChatGPT to create effective publications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Basic prompts to generate relevant content. ▪ Creation of examples of promotional publications and e-mails. 3. Case studies and customisation (30 minutes): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Live examples using common cases from participating companies. o Resolution of specific doubts and tips for immediate implementation.. <p>Session 2: Process optimisation and automation (90 minutes)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Review and collaborative learning (15 minutes): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Presentation of examples created by the participants in the first session. o Feedback and optimisation of the generated content. 2. Content planning and automation (60 minutes): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Creating a monthly publication plan in less than 15 minutes.. o Using tools such as Canva and Metricool to automate tasks. o Practical exercise: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Designing attractive images for social media. ▪ Generate batch publications using thematic categorisation techniques. 3. Closing and motivation (15 minutes): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Review of key tools learned. o Tips for integrating AI into daily management. o Resolution of final questions and assignment of practical tasks to apply what has been learned.
<p>Requirements :</p>	<p>Internet connection. E-mail account.</p>

General objective:	Help small businesses in the nautical tourism sector to incorporate and leverage AI tools such as ChatGPT to create content faster, improve their digital communication and optimise their working time.
Expected outcomes of the course:	To start using AI in their daily lives. Creating actionable digital strategies. Effective publishing and basic content automation.
Types of tools to use and cost for companies	Free tools such as Canva and Metricool (basic options). Optional: Paid version of ChatGPT (\$20/month) to maximise results.
Benefit to enterprises	Time saving in the creation and management of content. Improved online visibility and communication. Immediate application of practical tools adapted to your needs.
Link to video	https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fo/23258tgb62idm99jpg9d1/AAbFG920kDsaLJdH4X6M7Gs?rlkey=ln6o8gwzy3q4qwqyer37l5cuf&dl=0
Link to materials	Spanish https://enuno.notion.site/Tu-Br-jula-Digital-Primera-Sesion-1cb96880954080b19cadf99eecf8a0c5?pvs=4 English https://enuno.notion.site/Your-Digital-Compass-First-Session-1cc96880954080218c05eba776735363?pvs=4

COURSE FACT SHEET - HYDROPHONES

Course: Use of Hydrophones during whale watching acoustic experiences	Trainer: Misael Morales Vargas (Biosean)
Format: 2 online masterclasses + outings	Language: Spanish Available in French and Portuguese.
Target Audience: Small businesses in the nautical tourism sector in the Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira, and Martinique that are interested in integrating hydrophones into their experiences.	

<p>Content: This course is designed to introduce and train businesses in the use of hydrophones as an innovative tool to offer unique acoustic experiences during whale watching activities. It includes technical, environmental, and practical aspects, from installing and maintaining equipment to interpreting marine sounds and incorporating them into tourism activities.</p>	
<p>Duration: 80 minutes online class Few outings (from 2 to 4 hours each)</p>	<p>Activities to be carried out and duration of each one (theoretical online class, practical seminar, etc.):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 40 minutes online masterclass covering hydrophones types, modernization, use, installation on different boats, costs, maintenance, providers, etc.- 40 minutes online masterclass covering species in each region, storytellings, environment and stressors, marine sound interpretation.- Few outings (from 2 to 4 hours) once enterprises acquire and install the hydrophones.
<p>Requisites</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Businesses or associations interested in implementing hydrophones in their whale-watching activities.- Availability to purchase their own hydrophones, amplifiers and speakers (if needed), as these are not financed.
<p>General objective:</p>	<p>To train businesses in the nautical sector to incorporate marine acoustics into their whale-watching experiences, enhancing their tourism offerings and raising awareness about marine conservation.</p>
<p>Expected outcomes:</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Businesses are equipped with technical and narrative skills for using hydrophones.2. Improved customer experience through the integration of innovative technologies and educational content.3. Increased sustainability in whale-watching activities by fostering a deeper connection with the marine environment.4. Greater awareness of marine biodiversity and the factors affecting cetaceans in each region.
<p>Types of tools to use and cost for companies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Hydrophones: Each business must acquire its own equipment. Costs vary depending on the type and supplier, ranging from basic to advanced models.- Amplifiers, speakers and recorders (according to the company's needs).

Benefit to business	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Diversification of tourism offerings with a unique and innovative experience that appeals to environmentally and culturally conscious audiences. 2. Enhanced sustainability by including educational elements about marine life and conservation. 3. Positioning as pioneering businesses in acoustic marine tourism within their regions. 4. Added value through emotional and educational connections with customers as well as by incorporating another sense in the experience, not just the visual sense but also the hearing system.
---------------------	--

Course FACT Sheet: MARINE STARGUIDE

Course: MARINE STARGUIDE	Trainers: Xavier y Gerard Martínez NAUTIC OCEAN, Javier Ares from Polaris Menorca, Naty Sánchez from xxxx, Elena Ramos from SEO BIRD LIFE	
Format: Online	Language: Spanish Translation: into French and Portuguese	
Target Audience: - People and Small businesses in the nautical tourism sector from the Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira, and Martinique planning to implement or already offering an astrotourism product.		
Course Content (Subjects)		
Subject	Trainer	Duration (hours)
History of Astronomy	Javier Ares	1.5
Measuring Space-Time	Javier Ares	1.5
Basic Astronomy Course	Javier Ares	1.5
The Solar System	Javier Ares	1.5
How to Navigate the Sky	Javier Ares	1.5
Preparing an Observation with Stellarium	Javier Ares	1.5
History of Navigation	Xavier Martínez	2

Astrotourism and the Role of Certifications	Xavier Martínez	1
Nautical Astrotourism Marketing and Communication Skills	Gerard Martínez	3
Light Pollution	Elena Ramos	1
Mythology in Astronomical Navigation	Naty Sánchez	2
Duration: 18 hours of online training 1 practical field trip per region, approximately 3 hours.	MARINE STARGUIDE Instructor Certification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organization of an 18-hour online training course, delivered in collaboration with the Sabadell Astronomy Association. - Practical sessions in each region. One field trip per region. - Promotion of the Starlight Certification. 	
Cost: Free of charge	Requirements for MARINE STARGUIDE instructors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complete both the online and onsite training. - Prove their understanding of the topics taught in the practical part. 	
General Objective:	To promote the development of sustainable nautical astrotourism in the project regions by certifying territories and companies as Starlight (by the Fundación Starlight) and workers as Marine Starguide instructors, training specialized instructors, fostering innovative and responsible nighttime activities.	
Expected Course Outcomes:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Instructors certified as MARINE STARGUIDE instructors and nautical companies certified as Starlight: Businesses prepared to offer high-quality nautical astrotourism activities aligned with sustainability principles. 2. Trained and certified monitors: Professionals capable of leading nautical astrotourism activities, strengthening local human capital. 3. Creation of new nautical astrotourism activities: Diversifying the tourism offer with innovative proposals that integrate astronomy, nautical activities, and sustainability. 4. Increased visibility for participating businesses: Inclusion in the official App of the Starlight Foundation and the "Atlantic 	

	Starlight Adventures" digital platform, connecting companies with clients.
Tools to be Used and Costs for Businesses:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Necessary equipment for nighttime activities (telescopes, red-light flashlights, etc.).- Promotional material on the company's website (cost borne by the company).- After certification, businesses may join the Atlantic Starlight Adventures virtual platform.
Benefits for Businesses:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Recognition as a certified Marine StarGuide company and as a Starlight company (by the Fundación Starlight).2. Greater access to potential clients through inclusion in the official App of the Starlight Foundation and the Atlantic Starlight Adventures platform.3. Possibility to diversify tourism offers with sustainable, high value-added activities.4. Participation in an international star tourism network, increasing visibility and market credibility.

REFERENCES

- Auernhammer, J., & Roth, B. (2021). The origin and evolution of Stanford University's design thinking: From product design to design thinking in innovation management. *Journal of Product innovation management*, 38(6), 623-644.
- Brown, T. (2008). Design thinking. *Harvard business review*, 86(6), 84.
- Covarrubias Carmona, N. (2020). Wenuleufu: development of an experience for nature and adventure tourism through service design, case study: Rafting Río Bueno (Doctoral dissertation, Universidad de Chile).
- Enzyme Advising Group. (2023). *Design Thinking: Keys to its popularity*. <https://enzyme.biz/blog/design-thinking-claves-popularidad>
- Gano, G. (2015). Starting with Universe: Buckminster Fuller's Design Science Now. *Futures*, 70, 56-64.
- Goldman, S., Carroll, M., & Royalty, A. (2009, October). Destination, imagination & the fires within: Design thinking in a middle school classroom. In *Proceedings of the seventh ACM conference on Creativity and cognition* (pp. 371-372).
- Lalicic, L., Marine-Roig, E., Ferrer-Rosell, B., & Martin-Fuentes, E. (2021). Destination image analytics for tourism design: An approach through Airbnb reviews. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 86, 103100.
- López, M. I. H., & Pereyra, M. M. P. (2019). Applications of Design Thinking to service design for tourism: Integrating innovation, ergonomics and user experience. *Tsantsa. Journal of Artistic Research*, (7), 161-170.
- Micheli, P., Wilner, S. J., Bhatti, S. H., Mura, M., & Beverland, M. B. (2019). Doing design thinking: Conceptual review, synthesis, and research agenda. *Journal of Product innovation management*, 36(2), 124-148.
- Pacompia Chambi, A., & Ponce De Leon Chucuya, N. D. (2019). Study of Lean Startup and Design Thinking methodologies to generate entrepreneurship in students of the 5th year of the professional school of tourism and hospitality at the National University of San Agustin, Arequipa 2019.
- Panke, S. (2019). Design thinking in education: Perspectives, opportunities and challenges. *Open Education Studies*, 1(1), 281-306.
- Rusmann, A., & Ejsing-Duun, S. (2022). When design thinking goes to school: A literature review of design competences for the K-12 level. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 32(4), 2063-2091.
- Thomke, S., & Feinberg, B. (2009). Design thinking and innovation at apple. Harvard Business School Case, 609-066.
- Vinsel, L. (2018). There's so little there: A response to the Stanford D.School's defence of Design Thinking. Retrieved from <https://blog.usejournal.com/theres-so-little-there-there-a-response-to-the-stanford-d-school-s-defense-of-design-thinking-3cac35a1a365>

Watch&Act. (n.d.). *Design Thinking applied to Human Resources*.
<https://watchandact.eu/design-thinking-rrhh/>

Zupan, B., & Nabergoj, A. S. (2022). Design thinking as a course design methodology. In *Design Thinking* (pp. 17-39). CRC Press.
Lor, R. (2017). Design thinking in education: A critical review of literature.

TWINNED

By Stars

Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

Co-funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101124900. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.